

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1885	Jean Maspero	1910	1910	1915		French papyrologist	1885-1915
1885	Jean Przyluski	1911	1923	1938		Polish-French linguist and scholar of religion and Buddhism of Polish descent	1885-1944
1885	Cezaria Jędrzejewiczowa	1911	1922	1967	w	Polish scientist, art historian and anthropologist (one of the pioneers of ethnology in Poland, and adopt phenomenology in studies on the folk culture)	1885-1967
1885	John Alden Mason	1911	1911	1958		American archaeological anthropologist and linguist	1885-1967
1885	Margaret Hasluck	1912	1944	1945	w	British Scottish geographer, linguist, epigrapher, archaeologist and scholar, and spy	1885-1948
1885	Hermann Grapow	1912	1912	1962		German Egyptologist	1885-1967
1885	Edward Chiera	1913	1913	1933		Italian-American archaeologist, Assyriologist, and scholar of religions and linguistics	1885-1933
1885	Adam Chętnik	1913		1958		Polish ethnographer who studied the Kurpie	1885-1967
1885	Ebrahim Pourdavoud	1914		1960		Iranian founder the Iranology Society and, very soon afterwards, the School of Iranology	1885-1968
1885	Stith Thompson	1914	1914	1955		American scholar of folklore	1885-1976
1885	John Henry Hutton	1916	1921	1950		British English anthropologist and an administrator in the Indian Civil Service (ICS) during the period of the British Raj	1885-1968
1885	David Zolotarev	1916		1933		Russian anthropologist and ethnographer who studied the tribal populations of the Yaroslavl region of northern Russia	1885-1935
1885	Américo Castro	1916		1953		Spanish cultural historian, philologist, and literary critic	1885-1972
1885	Mary Paton Ramsay	1917		1946	w	British (Scottish) academic	1885-1946
1885	Giorgi Chubinashvili	1921		1973		Georgian art historian	1885-1973
1885	Rachel Wischnitzer	1922		1968	w	Belorussian-American architect and art historian	1885-1989
1885	Paul Collomp	1923	1926	1943		French scholar specialized in the history of Ptolemaic Kingdom	1885-1943
1885	Charles Kingsley Meek	1925		1950		British anthropologist	1885-1965
1885	Edward Hamilton Johnston	1907	1907	1942		British oriental scholar, the Boden Professor of Sanskrit	1885-1942
1885	Giorgio Pasquali	1907	1907	1952		Italian classical scholar who made a fundamental contribution to the field of textual criticism	1885-1952

1885	Franklin Edgerton	1909	1909	1954	American linguistic scholar, Salisbury Professor of Sanskrit and Comparative Philology	1885-1963
1886	Jan Rypka	1910	1910	1968	Czech orientalist, translator, professor of Iranology and Turkology	1886-1968
1886	Giulio Quirino Giglioli	1910	1910	1956	Italian art historian of classical Roman and Etruscan art and was associated with Fascism in Italy	1886-1957
1886	Erhard Lommatzsch	1910	1910	1955	German Romance philologist	1886-1975
1886	Fritz Neubert	1910	1910	1958	German Romanist	1886-1970
1886	Ernst Robert Curtius	1910	1910	1951	German literary scholar, philologist, and Romance language literary critic	1886-1956
1886	Francis Owen	1910	1910	1952	Canadian philologist and military officer	1886-1975
1886	Gotthelf Bergsträßer	1911		1933	German linguist specializing in Semitic studies	1886-1933
1886	Theodor Frings	1911	1911	1957	German Germanistic mediaevalist and linguist	1886-1968
1886	Hans Naumann	1911	1911	1949	German (Nazi) literary historian (philologist) and folklorist (Germanist)	1886-1951
1886	Henri Massé	1912		1958	French Orientalist	1886-1969
1886	Karl Polanyi	1912	1912	1958	Hungarian economic historian, economic anthropologist, economic sociologist, political economist, historical sociologist and social philosopher	1886-1964
1886	I. H. N. Evans	1912		1932	British anthropologist, ethnographer and archaeologist	1886-1957
1886	Ernst Buschor	1912	1912	1959	German archaeologist and translator	1886-1961
1886	André Boulanger	1913	1922	1958	French professor of literature and Latin scholar	1886-1958
1886	J. P. B. de Josselin de Jong	1913	No	1956	Dutch founding father of modern Dutch anthropology and of structural anthropology	1886-1964
1886	Philip K. Hitti	1915	1915	1954	Lebanese-American professor and scholar, and authority on Arab and Middle Eastern history, Islam, and Semitic languages	1886-1978
1886	Wilson Dallam Wallis	1915	1915	1954	American anthropologist, researcher in " primitive science " and religions	1886-1970
1886	Michelangelo Guidi	1916		1946	Italian Islamist and Arabist	1886-1946
1886	Diamond Jenness	1916	1916	1948	Canadian one of Canada's greatest early scientists and a pioneer of Canadian anthropology	1886-1969
1886	Richard Foster Jones	1918	1918	1945	American professor of English	1886-1965
1886	Josef Weninger	1918		1955	Austrian anthropologist	1886-1959

1886	Giorgio Levi Della Vida	1919		1959	Italian Jewish linguist whose expertise lay in Hebrew, Arabic, and other Semitic languages, as well as on the history and culture of the Near East	1886-1967
1886	Karl Barth	1919		1962	Swiss Reformed theologian	1886-1968
1886	Robert Pierpont Blake	1924		1950	American Byzantinist and scholar of the Armenian and Georgian cultures	1886-1950
1886	Martin Gusinde	1926	1926	1960	Austrian priest and ethnologist famous for his work in anthropology, particularly on the native groups of Tierra del Fuego	1886-1969
1886	Lila Morris O'Neale	1926	1930	1948 w	American anthropologist and historian of textiles	1886-1948
1886	Armand Machabey	1928	1928	1958	French 20th-century musicologist	1886-1966
1886	Max Vasmer	1907	1907	1956	German-Russian linguist	1886-1962
1886	Johannes Stroux	1907	1907	1954	German classicist, scholar of Roman law and organizer of scientific projects and organizations	1886-1954
1886	Otto Weinreich	1908	1908	1954	German classical philologist	1886-1972
1887	Luigi Pio Tessitori	1910	1910	1919	Italian Indologist and linguist	1887-1919
1887	E. V. Rieu	1910	No	1964	British classicist, publisher, poet and translator	1887-1972
1887	Ernest Hooton	1911	1911	1952	American physical anthropologist	1887-1954
1887	Jaime de Angulo	1911		1933	French-American linguist, novelist, and ethnomusicologist in the western United States	1887-1950
1887	George Groslier	1913		1942	French polymath who through his work as a painter, writer, historian, archaeologist, ethnologist, architect, photographer and curator	1887-1945
1887	Edward Winslow Gifford	1915	No	1955	American professor of anthropology (California Indian ethnography) and director of the Museum of Anthropology	1887-1959
1887	R. K. Gordon	1918		1950	British scholar of medieval and early modern English literature and administrator	1887-1973
1887	William James Perry	1918		1949	British leader in cultural anthropology	1887-1949
1887	Leon Feraru	1918	1929	1954	Romanian-American poet, literary historian and translator	1887-1962
1887	Gaston Wiet	1919		1951	French Orientalist	1887-1971
1887	Frederik Jacobus Johannes Buytendijk	1919	1919	1957	Dutch anthropologist, biologist and psychologist	1887-1974
1887	S. M. Shirokogoroff	1919		1939	Russian anthropologist	1887-1939

1887	Shinobu Orikuchi	1920	1934	1953	Japanese ethnologist, linguist, folklorist, novelist, and poet	1887-1953
1887	Akaki Shanidze	1920	1920	1987	Georgian linguist and philologist	1887-1987
1887	Werner Gruehn	1920	1927	1961	Latvian-German Professor of Protestant Theology and Psychology of Religion	1887-1961
1887	Ruth Benedict	1923	1923	1948 w	American anthropologist and folklorist	1887-1948
1887	Isabel Frances Grant	1924	No	1954 w	British Scottish ethnographer, historian, collector and pioneering founder of the Highland Folk Museum	1887-1983
1887	Leonard Bloomfield	1908	1909	1946	American linguist	1887-1949
1887	Julius Pokorny	1909	1910	1959	Austrian-Czech scholar of the Celtic languages, particularly Irish, and a supporter of Irish nationalism	1887-1970
1887	Günther Jachmann	1909	1909	1952	German classical philologist	1887-1979
1888	Werner Jaeger	1911	1911	1959	German classicist of the 20th century	1888-1961
1888	Friedrich Schür	1911	1911	1958	Austrian Romanist, Italianist und Dialektologist	1888-1980
1888	Eduard Brenner	1912	1912	1955	German professor of English, state secretary in the Bavarian State Ministry of Education and Culture (1951-1954)	1888-1970
1888	Benimadhab Barua	1912	1913	1948	Bangladeshi scholar of ancient Indian languages, Buddhism and law	1888-1948
1888	Charles Ambrose Storey	1912	1912	1947	British orientalist	1888-1968
1888	Eduard Fraenkel	1912		1953	German-British philologist	1888-1970
1888	Friedrich Winkler	1912	1912	1957	German art historian specialised in German art	1888-1965
1888	Franz Koch	1912	1912	1952	Austrian-German (Nazi) literary historian and scholar of Goethe and Schiller	1888-1969
1888	Alice Braunlich	1913	1913	1956 w	American classical philologist	1888-1989
1888	Marc Pincherle	1913	1913	1970	French musicologist, music critic and violinist	1888-1974
1888	Elisabeth Gerdts-Rupp	1913	1913	1959 w	German jurist, lyric poet and a respected ethnologist	1888-1972
1888	Zygmunt Czerny	1913	1913	1952	Polish romance philologist (with a specialization in the French language)	1888-1975
1888	Paul Althaus	1913	1913	1964	German Lutheran theologian	1888-1966
1888	Zdzisław Żygulski (senior)	1914	1914	1959	Polish literary historian and Germanist	1888-1975
1888	António Mendes Correia	1915	1922	1956	Portuguese anthropologist, physician and scientist	1888-1960
1888	Otto Rosenberg	1916	1918	1919	Russian scholar who created a system of organizing Chinese characters in a dictionary format, which eventually resulted in the Four Corner Method	1888-1919

1888 Franz Dornseiff	1916	1916	1960	German philologist	1888-1960
1888 E. O. James	1917	1924	1955	British anthropologist in the field of comparative religion	1888-1972
1888 Walther von Wartburg	1918	1918	1959	Swiss philologist and lexicographer	1888-1971
1888 Alfred Guillaume	1920		1955	British Arabist, scholar of Islam and Hebrew Bible / Old Testament scholar	1888-1965
1888 Ralph Lilley Turner	1920		1957	British Indian languages philologist and university administrator	1888-1983
1888 George Carver	1923		1949	American professor and author	1888-1949
1888 Jack Herbert Driberg	1923 No		1946	British anthropologist	1888-1946
1888 Germaine Rouillard	1923	1923	1946 w	French byzantinist specializing in philology	1888-1946
1888 Toma Smiljanić-Bradina	1924	1931	1946	Serbian (North Macedonian) ethnographer, philologist, dramatist and publicist	1888-1969
1888 Ursula McConnel	1926 No		1935 w	Australian the Queensland anthropologist and ethnographer best remembered for her work with, and the records she made of, the Wik Mungkan people of Cape York Peninsula	1888-1957
1888 Marius Canard	1927		1961	French Orientalist and historian	1888-1982
1888 James Madison Carpenter	1929	1929	1954	American the Methodist minister and scholar of American and British folklore	1888-1983
1888 Jinvijayji	1936		1967	Indian scholar of orientalism, archeology, indology and Jainism	1888-1976
1888 Bayard Dodge	1909	1909	1948	American scholar of Islam and president of the American University in Beirut	1888-1972
1889 Harold Gould Henderson	1910	1910	1955	American academic, art historian and Japanologist	1889-1974
1889 Tadeusz Jan Kowalski	1911	1911	1948	Polish orientalist, expert on Middle East Muslim culture and languages	1889-1948
1889 Fritz Krüger	1911	1911	1974	German Romanist and Hispanist	1889-1974
1889 Rudolf Pfeiffer	1913	1913	1957	German classical philologist	1989-1979
1889 Helmuth Theodor Bossert	1913	1913	1959	German art historian, philologist and archaeologist	1889-1961
1889 Elias Wessén	1914	1914	1956	Swedish linguist and a professor of Scandinavian languages	1889-1981
1889 Hyder Edward Rollins	1914	1915	1956	American scholar and English professor	1889-1958

1889 Sidney Smith	1914		1955	British Assyriologist (both a linguist and archeologist) who has been described as the architect of Mesopotamian studies	1889-1979
1889 Richard Offner	1914	1914	1961	Austrian-American art historian dedicated to the study of Florentine paintings from the Renaissance	1889-1965
1889 Josef Kroll	1914	1914	1956	German classical philologist and university rector	1889-1980
1889 William Edward Collinson	1914	1914	1954	British linguist (the International Auxiliary Language Association (IALA))	1889-1969
1889 Bernhard Karlgren	1915	1915	1959	Swedish sinologist and linguist who pioneered the study of Chinese historical phonology using modern comparative methods	1889-1978
1889 Mary-Russell Ferrell Colton	1918	No	1949 w	American artist, author, educator, ethnographer, and curator	1889-1971
1889 Adolphe Rome	1919	1919	1958	Belgian classical philologist and science historian (ancient history of astronomy)	1889-1971
1889 Johannes Sass	1920	1926	1956	German linguist who specialized in the Low German language	1889-1971
1889 Henri Victor Vallois	1920		1970	French anthropologist and paleontologist	1889-1981
1889 Gustav Indrebø	1921	1925	1942	Norwegian philologist	1889-1942
1889 William Lindsay Renwick	1921	1926	1959	British Professor of English Literature	1889-1970
1889 Erhard Preiig	1921	1921	1945	German Romanist	1889-1945
1889 Elizabeth Titzel Riefstahl	1923	No	1975 w	American anthropologist and archaeologist who specialized in artwork from the Near East	1889-1986
1889 Jose Miguel Barandiaran	1924		1991	Spanish Basque anthropologist, ethnographer, and priest	1889-1991
1889 Beatrice Blackwood	1927		1959 w	British anthropologist	1889-1975
1889 Joseph Salvat	1927		1972	French canonist, romanist and occitanist	1889-1972
1889 Stuart N. Wolfenden	1928	No	1938	American linguist, titular head of the Sino-Tibetan philology projec	1889-1938
1889 Ella Cara Deloria	1928	No	1961 w	American educator, anthropologist, ethnographer, linguist, and novelist of European American and Native American (American Indian) ancestry	1889-1971